

Deliverable 6.4

Cross-domain co-development of policy messages
for European ocean observing
- Clustering Event II

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Executive Summary

Developing integrated ocean observing across physics, biogeochemistry, and biology and ecosystems remains a major scientific, technical, operational, and governance challenge. Ocean observing systems have historically evolved through partially separate communities, infrastructures, standards, and policy pathways, limiting interoperability and integration across domains. At the same time, increasing societal and policy demands linked to climate change, biodiversity loss, pollution, and sustainable ocean management require more coordinated and integrated knowledge systems.

This deliverable presents the outcomes of Clustering Event II, a cross-domain co-development process carried out within the EOVS Network by the three Horizon Europe sister projects BioEcoOcean, ObsSea4Clim, and BioGeoSea, coordinated with support from EuroGOOS. The process aimed to strengthen integration across biological, biogeochemical, and physical ocean observing communities and to co-develop coordinated policy messages supporting the future evolution of the European ocean observing system, with a global outlook.

The co-development process consisted of three interconnected activities:

- An online EOVS Network Workshop held on 31 March 2026;
- The in-person Clustering Event II organised on 20-21 April 2026 in Brussels alongside the EuroGOOS General Assembly; and
- A stakeholder-focused workshop and exhibition activities at European Maritime Day (EMD) 2026 in Limassol, on 21-22 May 2026.

The activities brought together project partners, EuroGOOS members, regional systems, and communities, European institutions, blue economy stakeholders, and wider marine knowledge communities. Through co-design discussions, policy dialogues, and stakeholder engagement activities, participants identified shared priorities, barriers, enabling conditions, and strategic needs for advancing integrated ocean observing systems.

The discussions across all activities demonstrated strong convergence around several key priorities. Participants highlighted the need for:

- Stronger integration across physical, biogeochemical, and biological observing domains;
- Interoperable and FAIR-compliant data infrastructures and operational data flows;
- Improved links between observations, modelling, indicators, forecasting, and decision-support services;
- Stronger coordination across European and international governance structures;
- Sustained long-term investment and operational continuity;
- Improved connection and communication between ocean observing, policy, and society; and
- Stronger collaboration between research, operational oceanography, industry, and users.

The process also reinforced the importance of the Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) framework as a practical mechanism for supporting interoperability, integration, and policy relevance across observing domains and infrastructures. Discussions highlighted increasing recognition of ocean observing as a public good and strategic infrastructure underpinning climate adaptation and resilience, environmental protection, reliable forecasting and digital twin services, safety, and the sustainable blue economy.

Stakeholder exchanges at EMD 2026 further demonstrated strong demand for ocean observing systems that are more user-oriented, accessible, and capable of delivering actionable knowledge and services. At the same time, feedback collected through surveys and discussions revealed that awareness and uptake of both the EOV framework and FAIR data principles remain uneven beyond specialised communities, representing an important barrier to broader implementation and operational integration.

Clustering Event II activities demonstrated the value of structured cross-domain and stakeholder engagement processes in aligning priorities across projects and communities, strengthening interdisciplinary collaboration, and contributing coordinated input to European policy initiatives, including the Ocean Pact, OceanEye, and the Ocean Act.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics
DG MARE	Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
DG RTD	Directorate-General Research and Innovation
EBV	Essential Biodiversity Variables
ECV	Essential Climate Variables
EMD	European Maritime Day
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EOVs	Essential Ocean Variables
EuroGOOS	European Global Ocean Observing System
EuroGOOS ROOS	EuroGOOS Regional Operational Oceanographic System
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UU	Uppsala University

1. Introduction

Developing integrated ocean observing across physics, biogeochemistry, and biology and ecosystems remains a major scientific, technical, and governance challenge. These domains have historically evolved through partially separate observing communities, infrastructures, standards, operational practices, and policy pathways, often operating at different spatial and temporal scales and with different approaches to uncertainty, interoperability, and data management. At the same time, major societal and policy challenges, including climate change, biodiversity loss, pollution, resilience, forecasting, and sustainable ocean management, increasingly require integrated observations and assessments capable of linking processes, interactions, and variability across domains.

Within the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) provide a common international framework for defining the key physical, biogeochemical, and biological and ecosystem variables needed to systematically monitor and understand ocean state, variability, and change [1]. By linking observing requirements across domains, EOVs help support interoperability, coordination, and the development of integrated ocean knowledge and services [2].

Bridging the physics, biogeochemistry, and biology and ecosystems domains requires more than technological integration. It also requires structured collaboration across disciplines, observing communities, infrastructures, and governance systems, alongside shared frameworks, common standards, and sustained arenas for interdisciplinary exchange and co-development. Despite increasing recognition of this need within international and European ocean observing initiatives, practical examples of how such cross-domain collaboration can be conducted and operationalised remain limited. Through the EOV network, the three sister projects worked together to refine shared priorities, align policy messaging, strengthen collaboration across observing domains, and establish a structured platform for engagement with policymakers and other stakeholders.

This deliverable addresses this challenge through Clustering Event II, a cross-domain co-design process bringing together three EU-funded sister projects ObsSea4Clim, BioGeoSea, and BioEcoOcean within the EOV network [2, 3]. The process focused on how collaboration across physics, biogeochemistry, and biology and ecosystems can support the development of integrated and policy-relevant observing systems, while also identifying barriers, enabling conditions, and emerging policy needs.

Clustering Event II builds on the outcomes of Clustering Event I held in March 2025 in Sopot [2], which brought together BioEcoOcean and ObsSea4Clim, with BioGeoSea invited as a forthcoming sister project. The first event established a shared understanding of EOVs interdependencies across physics, biogeochemistry, biology and ecosystems, and demonstrated the value of interactive formats such as EOVs “speed-dating” and panel discussions.

Clustering Event I highlighted challenges that go beyond individual projects, including fragmentation across observing systems, scale mismatches, interoperability gaps, uneven EOVS maturity, limited integration of biological and ecosystem observations, and weak links between observations, indicators, assessments and policy applications. The discussions also reinforced the importance of EOVS as a common framework for connecting observations across domains and supporting integrated ocean knowledge.

Building on these foundations, Clustering Event II was designed as a stepwise co-development process, focused on translating identified challenges into policy-relevant activities.

The stepwise co-development process consisted of three interconnected components:

1. Online EOVS Network workshop on 31 March 2026

This workshop initiated the co-design process by involving members of the three sister projects in identifying shared priorities, joint actions, and policy needs for cross-domain (physics, biogeochemistry, biology and ecosystems) EOVS integration.

2. In-person Clustering Event II on 20–21 April 2026, Brussels

Held back-to-back with the EuroGOOS General Assembly, the event consolidated workshop outcomes, aligned cross-project policy messages, and facilitated dialogue between the EOVS projects and key European actors, including EuroGOOS Members, ROOS, Working Groups and Task Teams, alongside policy representatives from the European Commission (DG MARE and DG RTD) and the European Environment Agency (EEA). These discussions focused on the role of the EOVS framework within the broader ocean observing system and its alignment with key European policy initiatives. The event focused on four main areas: (i) interoperable data and indicators; (ii) coordinated stakeholder and policy engagement; (iii) legacy pathways anchored in European ocean observing governance through EuroGOOS; and (iv) community input to ongoing EU policy developments, including the Ocean Pact, OceanEye (Ocean Observation Initiative), the R&I Strategy and the Ocean Act, as well as Copernicus priorities and requirements. Furthermore, the event aimed to agree on practical steps towards shared best practices and EOVS Network outputs (e.g., joint statements, coordinated priorities, policy-relevant messages).

3. Stakeholder engagement at European Maritime Day (EMD) on 22 May 2026, Limassol

Recommendations emerging from the previous steps, were highlighted and discussed with a broader stakeholder community at the science-policy interface at a dedicated EOVS Network Workshop titled “Shaping Ocean Observing Needs with Blue Economy”. Organised by EuroGOOS for the EOVS Network, the workshop brought together three projects and diverse stakeholders in international cooperation, fisheries, data, policy, and research. The workshop was complemented by stakeholder engagement through the EMD stand, organised by the EOVS Network.

2. Co-production and co-design of EOV Network policy recommendations

2.1 EOV Network Workshop

The Online EOV Network workshop on 31 March 2026 brought together partners from the three sister projects BioEcoOcean, ObsSea4Clim and BioGeoSea within the EOV Network to initiate the co-development of policy recommendations on cross-domain ocean observing aligned with key EU frameworks, including the Ocean Pact and OceanEye (Ocean Observation Initiative). The workshop also served as a capacity-building and knowledge-sharing exercise, ensuring a common understanding of ongoing and emerging EU ocean policy processes across the three projects.

Purpose and rationale

The workshop was designed to address a central challenge facing the ocean observing community: how to operationalise integration across biological, biogeochemical, and physical observing systems, and translate this integration into policy-relevant outputs. While the importance of integrated ocean observing is widely recognised, its implementation remains constrained by fragmentation across disciplines, infrastructures and governance levels, as well as persistent gaps between data generation and policy uptake. Against this background, the workshop aimed to move beyond conceptual discussions to co-develop actionable priorities and recommendations that reflect both scientific realities and policy needs.

Methodology

The workshop applied a structured co-design/co-production methodology, combining plenary discussions and breakout sessions for brainstorming, policy mapping, cross-domain exchange, and joint prioritisation. Three rounds of breakout session discussions were conducted. Participants first aligned ongoing activities across the three sister projects with key EU policy frameworks, including the Ocean Pact, OceanEye, and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). Round two followed with cross-disciplinary discussions to identify shared challenges, gaps, and opportunities for joint actions within the projects, with each group focusing on one of specific themes, namely: (i) integration of physics, biogeochemistry, and biodiversity observations; (ii) uptake and adoption of EOVs and indicators; (iii) data integration, FAIR data principles, and uncertainty; (iv) integrating physics, biogeochemistry, and biology and ecosystems in products. Building on this, participants co-developed joint policy priorities and enabling conditions required to advance integrated ocean observing systems.

Key findings and outcomes

Discussions confirmed that the main barriers to cross-domain EOV integration are not primarily scientific, but systemic and structural. Key challenges identified across all groups included fragmentation across observing domains and governance levels, gaps in data interoperability and implementation of FAIR

principles, lack of standardised approaches to uncertainty, insufficient long-term funding, and weak science-policy interfaces.

The workshop resulted in a set of converging outcomes across the three projects, structured around six core areas:

1. Standardisation and interoperability across ocean observing systems

Advancing the harmonisation of metadata frameworks, controlled vocabularies, observing methods, best practices, and approaches to uncertainty, to enable interoperability and integration across biological, biogeochemical, and physical domains.

2. Integrated indicators and data products

Co-developing multi-EOV indicators (e.g., for marine heatwaves and ocean carbon processes) and interoperable data products, linking physical, biogeochemical, and biological observations, and aligning with FAIR principles and data infrastructures (e.g., EMODnet, OBIS, and Copernicus services).

3. Integration across the full ocean observing value chain

Strengthening connections from observations to data systems, modelling, indicators, and decision-support tools, including improved integration between observations, models, and applications to produce coherent and scalable outputs.

4. Cross-project collaboration and co-design mechanisms

Enhancing collaboration across projects through joint case studies, shared methodologies, targeted workshops, and knowledge exchange, and promoting sustained interdisciplinary co-design processes to support integration in practice.

5. Science-policy interface and uptake of EOVs

Strengthening mechanisms to translate observations into policy-relevant indicators and products and supporting the integration of EOVs into EU policy frameworks, including the MSFD and the Ocean Pact.

6. Governance, coordination, and sustained investment

Recognising ocean observing as a public good, requiring sustained and coordinated investment, strengthened governance and coordination mechanisms across EU and national levels, and long-term funding for observing infrastructures, data systems, and collaborative structures.

Across all areas, participants emphasised that progress depends on sustained funding mechanisms beyond project cycles, strengthened coordination across EU initiatives and national systems, cross-EOV interoperable data infrastructures, including implementation of FAIR principles and systematic data-sharing, and dedicated structures to support interdisciplinary collaboration and co-design, supporting regional synthesis, management, and policy action. A first set of policy messages addressing these priorities was developed and further discussed at the second step of the co-development process, i.e. the in-person Clustering Event II on 20-21 April 2026.

Overall, the online workshop provided a concrete framework for translating scientific collaboration into policy-relevant solutions. It played an important role in aligning the three projects around shared priorities, strengthening the EOVS Network as a platform for integration, and positioning the EOVS framework as a key building block for a coordinated, policy-relevant, sustained, and integrated European Ocean Observing System.

2.2 In-person Clustering Event II

The in-person EOVS Network Clustering Event II on 20-21 April 2026, held at the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, Brussels, Belgium, and hosted by EuroGOOS, was organised back-to-back with the EuroGOOS General Assembly. The event built on the outcomes of the online workshop (see Section 2.1) and advanced the co-development of joint policy messages across the three EOVS sister projects.

The event brought together project partners in an internal coordination workshop on 20 April and during the EuroGOOS General Assembly Special Session on 21 April, welcoming EuroGOOS Members, Regional Operational Oceanographic Systems (ROOS), Working Groups, and Task Teams, alongside representatives from the European Commission (DG MARE and DG RTD) and the European Environment Agency (EEA).

The event aimed to consolidate and refine the priorities identified during the online workshop, align cross-project messaging towards European policy processes, and strengthen dialogue between the EOVS sister projects and key European actors shaping the future of ocean observation and marine knowledge governance. Particular attention was given to the role of the EOVS framework in supporting a more integrated, coordinated and sustained European Ocean Observing System, in the context of emerging initiatives such as the European Ocean Pact, OceanEye, the Ocean Act, and evolving Copernicus priorities.

Structured around an internal coordination workshop and interactive panel discussions with policymakers, the event provided a platform to further articulate common priorities across biological, biogeochemical, and physical observing communities, while positioning the EOVS Network as a mechanism for integration across domains, infrastructures, and policy frameworks.

Purpose and rationale

The in-person Clustering Event II was conceived as a transition point from exploratory exchange towards strategic alignment and policy engagement across the EOVS Network. While the online workshop focused on identifying shared challenges, integration needs, and preliminary priorities across the three projects, the in-person meeting aimed to consolidate these discussions into a more coherent set of joint messages and recommendations targeted at European policy and governance processes.

The event also reflected the increasing policy relevance of ocean observing at the European level. With initiatives such as the European Ocean Pact, OceanEye, and the Ocean Act shaping discussions on the future governance of ocean knowledge and observing systems, Clustering Event II provided a timely opportunity

for the EOV sister projects to engage directly with policymakers and contribute coordinated scientific perspectives to these evolving processes.

A further rationale for the event was the recognition that achieving integrated ocean observing requires coordination not only across scientific domains, but also across infrastructures, governance structures, operational frameworks, and stakeholder communities. In this context, the event sought to strengthen cross-domain coherence within the EOV Network, improve alignment between research and operational communities, and explore the enabling conditions needed for sustained and policy-relevant observations.

Methodology

The in-person Clustering Event II was designed as a complementary and follow-up step to the online EOV Network workshop held on 31 March 2026. While the online workshop focused on broad cross-project exchange, identification of shared challenges, and the initial co-development of priorities and policy messages through structured co-design discussions, the Brussels event concentrated on consolidating these outcomes, refining joint messages, and aligning with ongoing European policy and governance discussions.

The event combined internal coordination sessions and interactive policy dialogues to support both cross-project alignment and engagement with external stakeholders. Day 1 (20 April) focused on synthesis-oriented discussions among the three EOV sister projects to review and refine the outcomes of the online workshop, identify priorities for further collaboration, and prepare coordinated inputs for engagement with policymakers. Day 2 (21 April) integrated the EOV Network discussions into the EuroGOOS General Assembly through interactive panel sessions involving representatives from the European Commission, the European Environment Agency, EuroGOOS Members, and the wider ocean observing community.

Clustering Event II - internal workshop on 20 April 2026, Brussels, Belgium

EuroGOOS General Assembly, 21-22 April 2026, Brussels, Belgium

The methodology combined synthesis presentations, moderated discussions, collaborative reflection, and direct exchanges with policymakers. This approach enabled validation and further development of the priorities identified during the online workshop, while strengthening connections between science and operational oceanography, governance, and emerging European policy initiatives.

Key findings and outcomes

Discussions during the in-person Clustering Event II confirmed a strong convergence across the three EOVS sister projects regarding the need for a more integrated, coordinated, and operational European Ocean Observing System. Dialogues were structured around several interconnected areas:

1. Embedding EOVS in ocean observing governance and policy frameworks

Discussions reinforced the importance of positioning the EOVS framework as a central organising principle for the European contribution to GOOS. Participants stressed the need to focus on variables, observing requirements, and phenomena rather than individual observing networks, enabling a more integrated and system-level approach across domains and infrastructures. The importance of embedding EOVS and associated indicators into European policy frameworks, operational services, and assessment systems was repeatedly highlighted.

2. Cross-domain integration through phenomena-based approaches

Participants emphasised that integration across biological, biogeochemical, and physical observing systems should increasingly be driven by the study of interconnected ocean phenomena and compound stressors. Discussions highlighted the importance of deriving integrated indicators and improving understanding of interactions between physical, biological, and biogeochemical processes. The need to improve EOVS literacy, including clearer communication around EOVS, Essential Climate Variables (ECVs), and Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) and their respective roles, was also identified.

3. Integrated observing systems and observing gaps

Discussions highlighted persistent challenges linked to integrating observing systems across disciplines, as they currently operate at different temporal and spatial scales and geographical locations. Participants stressed the need for closer integration between in situ observations, Earth observation systems, and digital infrastructures. Greater collaboration with the satellite observation community was identified as essential, alongside improved co-design of observing systems. Key gaps highlighted included deep ocean and subsurface observations, Arctic observations, oxygen observations, and biological observing capacity. Participants highlighted the potential of downscaling and gap-filling techniques, including AI-based approaches, noting that such methods are already widely applied in the biogeochemistry community, particularly in relation to carbon cycle observations and analysis.

4. Operationalisation and end-to-end value chains

The event reinforced the need to strengthen the full ocean observing value chain, from observations, as well as data collection and data publishing, to their uptake in modelling, forecasting, indicators, digital services, and decision-support systems. Discussions highlighted the need for a shift from predominantly science-driven approaches towards more operationally oriented systems capable of supporting sustained services, climate assessments, forecasting, and policy implementation. Improving timeliness and near-real-time delivery of observations and reducing latency between data collection and operational use were identified as major priorities.

5. Data interoperability, FAIR implementation, and incentives for open data

Participants highlighted persistent challenges related to data interoperability, alignment of variables and metadata from different disciplines throughout processing chains, and incentives for open data sharing, particularly in biological observing communities where FAIR implementation remains limited. Discussions stressed the importance of improving data literacy, strengthening incentives and recognition systems for data publication, and increasing support, funding, and capacity building for data management, QA/QC processes, and FAIR/CARE implementation.

6. Science-policy-society interfaces and adequacy assessments

Discussions highlighted the importance of strengthening dialogue between observing communities, policymakers, operational actors, users, industry, and society. Participants stressed the need for regular “stocktake” or adequacy assessment processes evaluating the maturity, coverage, and performance of observing systems against user and policy needs. The importance of co-defining observing requirements with users and communicating more clearly the societal, operational, and economic value of ocean observing systems was repeatedly emphasised, including their contribution to resilience, forecasting, digital twins, AI applications, and the blue economy.

7. Governance, coordination, resilience, and sustained investment

Discussions highlighted the need for stronger coordination mechanisms across European and national levels, including improved alignment among Member States, observing networks, regional structures, and international frameworks such as GOOS. Participants stressed that ocean observing should be recognised and supported as a public good requiring long-term and sustainable investment. The importance of coordinated European governance structures, including the proposed Member State Forum under the Ocean Act, was highlighted. Discussions also emphasised the need to strengthen the resilience of the global observing system, reduce dependency on individual external contributors, support European innovation ecosystems including SMEs and sensor developers, and foster stronger coordination between research, operations, and industrial actors.

Overall, participants stressed that future progress depends on sustained investment beyond project cycles, stronger coordination across fragmented observing and governance structures, improved interoperability and operational integration, and inclusive collaboration mechanisms involving marine knowledge communities, operational actors, policymakers, industry, and end users. The event also confirmed the importance of positioning the EOV framework within European and international discussions on the future governance, coordination, operationalisation, and resilience of ocean observing systems.

The event played an important role in consolidating the EOV Network's priorities, strengthening cross-project alignment, and advancing dialogue between the observing community and European policymakers. The event further demonstrated the value of the EOV framework as an effective mechanism for supporting integrated and sustained ocean observing across domains and sectors in Europe and beyond.

2.3 EMD 2026 Workshop

The workshop "Shaping Ocean Observing Needs with Blue Economy" was organised at the European Maritime Day 2026 (EMD) in Limassol, Cyprus, by the three sister projects in collaboration with EuroGOOS. The session brought together experts from ocean science, operational oceanography, policy, and blue economy sectors to discuss how Europe's ocean observing systems can become more integrated, operational, user-oriented, and societally relevant. The workshop explored how observing priorities should increasingly reflect the needs of policy, industry, and blue economy.

Purpose and Rationale

The workshop was developed from the recognition that ocean observing is moving higher on the European political agenda through initiatives such as the European Ocean Pact, OceanEye, the future Ocean Act, and digital ocean initiatives such as Europe's Digital Twin Ocean. At the same time, significant challenges remain across European ocean observing systems, including fragmentation between observing infrastructures, interoperability gaps, disconnects between disciplines and sea basins, and insufficient operational continuity.

The workshop aimed to broaden the EOV framework advancements and making them more relevant by involving blue economy actors, policymakers, operational services, and societal stakeholders. It identified what ocean information is most needed, how observations should be prioritised, and how ocean observing can better support services, investments, decision-making, and sustainable ocean management.

The rationale was also linked to the increasing recognition that ocean observing is not only a scientific or environmental activity, but also a public good and a strategic infrastructure supporting resilience, competitiveness, environmental protection, climate adaptation, maritime operations, and the sustainable blue economy.

Methodology

The workshop combined short expert pitches, panel discussion, audience interaction, and participatory feedback mechanisms (dedicated Mentimeter polls both prior and during the event). The session opened with an introduction to the EOV framework and the presentation of findings from a pre-event survey involving participants from research, policy, operational oceanography, blue economy, and civil society across several European sea basins. The survey highlighted strong demand for more integrated, interoperable, near-real-time, and user-oriented ocean observing systems.

BioEcoOcean, ObsSea4Clim, and BioGeoSea presented complementary perspectives on future ocean observing systems, focusing on the integration of observations across domains, readiness to support timely climate assessments and operational services, and integration with forecasting and services.

The workshop used panel discussions and Mentimeter tools to engage participants in identifying priorities, missing observations, user needs, and future expectations for European ocean observing. Discussions explored themes including:

- Integration across observing domains;
- Operationalisation of observing systems;
- Co-design with blue economy actors;
- Production of actionable indicators and services;
- Governance and investment priorities; and
- Public-good dimensions of ocean observations.

The workshop also emphasised collaboration and communication between scientists, operational actors, businesses, policymakers, and broad users as essential conditions for effective marine knowledge generation.

In addition to the workshop, the three EOV Network sister projects jointly organised an exhibition stand at the EMD, which served as an additional platform for stakeholder engagement, outreach, and feedback collection.

Key Findings and Outcomes

The workshop discussions and interactive Mentimeter exchanges revealed strong convergence around several strategic priorities for the future of European ocean observing. Participants consistently emphasised that ocean observing must increasingly deliver not only data, but actionable knowledge, operational services, insights, forecasts, and decision support capable of informing climate adaptation, environmental governance, maritime operations, sustainable blue economy activities, and public policy.

A dominant message emerging throughout the workshop was the urgent need for sustained long-term funding and operational continuity of the European ocean observing capabilities. Participants identified sustained funding and continuity of observations as critical priorities. It was also mentioned that

fragmentation across European ocean observing and data systems remains a major challenge. Participants stressed the importance of stronger coordination, standardisation, interoperability, harmonised frameworks, and improved data sharing across observing domains and sea basins.

The need for integrated approaches linking physical, biogeochemical, and biological observations was highlighted as essential for building coherent and operational marine knowledge systems capable of supporting both science and policy.

The discussions also demonstrated strong demand for ocean observing systems that are more user-focused, accessible, and responsive. Stakeholders highlighted usability, actionable data, operational knowledge, and co-design with users as key directions for the system evolution. Ocean observing systems should evolve beyond fragmented infrastructures toward integrated systems supporting multiple communities including policymakers, operational services, coastal managers, businesses, investors, civil society, and local communities.

Audience feedback at the “Shaping Ocean Observing Needs with Blue Economy” workshop at EMD 2026, 22 May 2026, Limassol, Cyprus

Biodiversity, biology, and ecosystem observations emerged as areas where participants perceived particularly significant gaps, including climate impacts, carbon budget, deep-sea and under-ice observations, ecosystem dynamics, and coastal observations. This reinforced the BioEcoOcean’s relevance in advancing and integrating biological and ecosystem observing capabilities along with data management

following FAIR and CARE practices, alongside integration and synergies with physical and biogeochemical observations.

The workshop also highlighted ocean observing as strategic infrastructure and a public good, reflecting the shift in policy recognition of observations not only as a scientific activity but also as an essential foundation for climate resilience, environmental management, maritime safety, economic competitiveness, and informed decision-making.

“Shaping Ocean Observing Needs with Blue Economy” workshop at EMD 2026, 22 May 2026, Limassol, Cyprus

EOV Network Booth at EMD 2026, 21-22 May 2026, Limassol, Cyprus

At the EMD exhibition stand jointly hosted by the EOVS Network projects and EuroGOOS, some of the visitors were surveyed to better understand their degree of familiarity with the EOVS framework, FAIR data practices, and the type of organisations they represented. In total, 19 visitors were interviewed. Results showed that awareness of the EOVS framework remains uneven across the visitors spanning research, private sector, and NGOs, with 47% of respondents reporting no familiarity with EOVS. Similarly, familiarity with FAIR data practices was relatively low, with 71% of respondents indicating limited or no knowledge of FAIR data management principles. While the survey sample was small, the results reflect a broader concern already recorded through stakeholder interactions across the EOVS Network: both FAIR principles and the EOVS framework remain insufficiently understood and adopted beyond specialised communities, creating an important barrier to wider implementation and operational integration.

3. Policy Messages

The discussions across the online workshop, the in-person Clustering Event II, and the EMD workshop highlighted a strong convergence around the need for a more integrated, operational, and strategically coordinated European Ocean Observing System. The following policy messages emerged from the exchanges between the three EOVS sister projects, EuroGOOS structures, operational actors, policymakers, and blue economy stakeholders.

- **Ocean observing is increasingly becoming a strategic European policy and operational priority**
Ocean observation is key for the evolving European initiatives, including the Ocean Pact, the Ocean Act, OceanEye, Copernicus developments, and broader discussions on resilience, competitiveness, and environmental governance.
- **Integration across observing domains requires a shift from fragmented systems towards coordinated, phenomena-based approaches**
Integration should increasingly focus on interconnected ocean phenomena and societal needs rather than isolated disciplinary or network-based approaches. Improved coordination across physical, biogeochemical, and biological and ecosystem observations was identified as essential for supporting integrated assessments, predictive modelling and forecasting, and policy-relevant services.
- **Ocean observing systems are evolving from research-driven activities towards sustained operational infrastructures**
Ocean observing needs to be recognised as a sustained operational system supporting forecasting, climate assessments, digital services, and decision-making. This requires stronger integration between research and operational oceanography so that observations more effectively support continuous, standardised, and service-oriented delivery of data, forecasts, indicators, and services.
- **Interoperability, FAIR implementation, and operational data flows remain critical enabling conditions for integrated, sustained observing systems**
Challenges persist related to interoperability across observing systems, implementation of FAIR and CARE principles, alignment of variables and standards, and near-real-time operational data delivery. These remain major barriers to integration and operationalisation. Key priorities include strengthening international collaboration, supporting data publishing and uptake of standards and FAIR principles, reinforcing governance structures, investing in interoperable digital infrastructures, and expanding capacity-building efforts.
- **The value of ocean observing needs to be communicated more clearly across policy and society**
There is a need to strengthen connections between ocean observing, policy, and society, and improve communication around the societal, operational, and economic value of ocean observing systems, including their contribution to resilience, protection of lives and ecosystems, forecasting services, AI-enabled applications, digital twins, and the sustainable blue economy.
- **Sustained coordination and governance mechanisms are required at European and international levels**
Fragmentation across observing systems, governance structures, and funding mechanisms limits the integration, efficiency, and long-term sustainability of ocean observing. Stronger coordination

is needed across Member States, regional systems, observing networks, European infrastructures, and international frameworks such as GOOS, supported by resilient governance arrangements and coordinated long-term investment approaches.

- **Innovation and technology are strategic elements of future ocean observing systems**

Innovation ecosystems linked to ocean observing, including sensor development, AI-enabled integration approaches, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), operational services, and digital infrastructures, are essential for advancing integrated and sustained observing systems. Technological innovation and strengthened operational capacity are also needed to address persistent gaps, particularly in the deep ocean, the Arctic region, and in subsurface, biogeochemical, and biological observations.

4. Conclusion

Clustering Event II brought together the three EU-funded sister projects BioEcoOcean, ObsSea4Clim, and BioGeoSea in a three-step co-development process aimed at advancing cross-domain policy messages for European ocean observing. The process combined an online EOVS Network Workshop, and in-person Clustering Event linked to the EuroGOOS General Assembly, and a stakeholder-oriented workshop and exhibition activities at the European Maritime Day 2026.

Together, these activities demonstrated the value of structured co-design and co-production processes for strengthening collaboration across biological, biogeochemical, and physical observing communities, while also connecting research, operational oceanography, policy, industry, and wider societal stakeholders. The process enabled the projects to consolidate shared priorities, refine coordinated policy messages, and strengthen the positioning of the EOVS framework as a practical mechanism for supporting integrated and policy-relevant ocean observing systems.

The discussions confirmed strong convergence around several strategic priorities. These include the need for more integrated and interoperable observing systems, stronger coordination across governance and observing structures, sustained long-term funding and operational continuity, improved implementation of FAIR and CARE principles, strengthened science-policy-society interfaces, and greater operationalisation of ocean observations into services, indicators, forecasting systems, and decision-support tools.

The process also reinforced the growing recognition that ocean observing should be treated not only as a scientific activity, but as strategic operational infrastructure and a public good underpinning climate resilience, environmental management, maritime safety, sustainable blue economy activities, and informed policymaking. At the same time, stakeholder exchanges highlighted persistent challenges linked to fragmentation, uneven uptake of EOVS and FAIR practices, data interoperability, and the integration of biological and ecosystem observations into sustained operational systems.

Overall, Clustering Event II and its associated activities demonstrated the importance of sustained interdisciplinary collaboration and structured stakeholder engagement in shaping the future of European ocean observing. The process further strengthened the EOVS Network as a platform for cross-domain integration and contributed coordinated community input to evolving European policy discussions around the Ocean Pact, OceanEye, and Ocean Act, and the future governance and operationalisation of ocean observing systems in Europe and beyond.

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6. References

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Partners

